

Fostering Academic Excellence: Unraveling the Nexus Between Teacher Job Satisfaction and Work Performance in Higher Education through Hertzberg's Theory

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
August 10, 2023

Accepted:
November 11, 2023

Keywords :

Job Satisfaction,
Employees Work
Performance, TheIslamia
University of Bahawalpur,
Pakistan.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10073623

Abstract

The most important problem in South Punjab's thriving higher education industry is not just having subject teachers but rather cultivating a motivated teaching staff ready for greatness. This study aims to explore the impact of teachers' job satisfaction practices on teachers work performance in Pakistan, depicting this relationship through a multidimensional construct and identify which dimension of job satisfaction are the predictor of teachers work Performance.

Design/methodology/approach – A cross-sectional survey was conducted across various schools in Pakistan, employing a quantitative approach that utilized a Job satisfaction questionnaire (TJSQ) developed by Lester (1982) adapted. Additionally, the 'Teacher Work Performance Questionnaire,' formulated by the researcher after studying the literature of different researchers such as Edwin A. Locke, Gary P. Latham, and Michael Armstrong, was developed as a secondary instrument to assess work performance. This study used a quantitative method with structural equation model (SEM) analysis on 165 teachers in south Punjab, Pakistan.

Findings – The study assessed job satisfaction across multiple dimensions, including supervision, colleagues, working conditions, salary and incentives, responsibility, the nature of the work, advancement opportunities, job security, recognition, and overall job satisfaction. The research findings highlighted that out of these dimensions, only three significantly influenced work performance: advancement, responsibility, and the nature of the work itself. The path causal model revealed that these variables mutually strengthened each other's impact. The study found that job satisfaction, in conjunction with work performance, explained 50% of the variance in the initial model. However, after removing dimensions with low values, the R-squared value decreased to 30%. The remaining 70% of the variance was attributed to unexamined factors. Notably, job satisfaction had its most significant impact on teachers' work performance through the quality of work, task execution, problem-solving, and adaptability. These results emphasize the pivotal role of job satisfaction in enhancing teachers' work performance, particularly in these key aspects of their professional lives.

Practical implications – Highly satisfied teachers tend to be more motivated and effective. This study introduces a causal model focused on integrating job satisfaction into Pakistan's education system. This model offers valuable insights to Pakistani university policymakers, helping them develop strategies based on factors influencing and influenced by teacher job satisfaction.

Originality/value – This article empirically constructs a causal model, exploring the impact of job satisfaction practices on teachers' work performance in Pakistani universities. This study bridges the gap between these two fields, and, to the researcher's knowledge, is the first of its kind within Pakistan's educational context.

Introduction

Locke(1976), “job satisfaction is characterized as a state of pleasurable or positive emotions that arises from assessing one's job or job-related experiences”. Locke's definition implicitly underscores the significance of both emotions (affect) and thought (cognition). In essence, when we experience emotions, we engage in corresponding thoughts about those emotions. This interconnection between cognition and affect is deeply

intertwined, not only in our psychological processes but also in our biological responses. Consequently, when we evaluate our jobs, just as when we assess other crucial aspects of our lives, both thinking and feeling play integral roles. Job satisfaction is more about the workers' attitude towards their jobs and their approach. In general, it is delineated as the assessments of individuals towards their jobs, whether "positive or negative". Favorable feelings regarding a job reflect job contentment, while unfavorable sentiments signify job discontentment. Teachers are the main factor in shaping the students' educational achievement in schools and satisfied teachers are instrumental in ensuring improved educational outcomes (Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee, 2020). Mahmood, Ismail and Omar Fauzee (2019) found that employees tend to improve and perform more effectively when managers employ participatory approaches to control and motivate their workforce using various reward systems. This was observed across a range of job satisfaction scales. (Hackman & Oldman, 1975; Herzberg, 1979; Maslow & Frager, 1987; Spector, 1985), "include such facets as the nature of work, promotion opportunities, security, and social relations".

In today's competitive landscape, employee performance and job satisfaction are paramount for achieving educational goals. The value of human resources has surpassed material assets, with organizations recognizing their significance in enhancing performance amid global competition and a dynamic business environment. Cultivating a positive working relationship with employees contributes to social sustainability. Skilled and motivated employees are scarce resources, driving modern businesses to prioritize sustainable human resource practices for a competitive edge.

Human development, encompassing education, training, a favorable work environment, fair compensation, and a strong corporate culture, plays a pivotal role in achieving social sustainability (Ullah et al., 2021). Effective employee management, fostering positive attitudes like increased productivity and job satisfaction while mitigating negative behaviors such as turnover and absenteeism, is a primary organizational goal. Achieving this relies on robust management and implementing empowering systems. Human resources embody employees' skills and experiences, with a conducive work environment and technology advancement further motivating and enabling them to excel (Tyagi, Chilamkurti, Grima, Sood, & Balusamy, 2023; Wright, Cropanzano, occupational, 2007). Notably, the work environment significantly influences employee job satisfaction, driving their commitment to company objectives (Jabbar, Mahmood, & Qambar, 2020).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The most important problem in South Punjab's thriving higher education industry is not just having subject teachers but rather cultivating a motivated teaching staff ready for greatness (Mahmood & Ismail, 2022). The main issue statement in this research is representative of the educational environment. "To what extent does teacher job satisfaction, as influenced by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, impact and shape work performance within higher education institutions in South Punjab?" The relationship between teacher job happiness and productivity is crucial to South Punjab's progress toward academic success. Understanding the depth and breadth of this connection is essential, since it is essential to improving the quality of education offered by these institutions. By addressing this issue statement, this research aims to decipher the complex relationships between job satisfaction, and work performance among South Punjabi instructors, therefore advancing education in the area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theories of Job Satisfaction

Maslow's Theory (1987):

In accordance with this theory, individuals possess five fundamental needs, which are as follows:

Physiological needs: These encompass the necessities related to physical and emotional well-being, such as a fair wage, food, shelter, clothing, and favorable working conditions.

Security needs: These pertain to the need for physical and emotional security and protection, including fair treatment, safeguards against threats, and job security.

Affiliation needs: This category includes the desire for affection, a sense of belonging, acceptance, and friendship, reflecting the need to feel loved, accepted, and part of a social group.

Esteem needs: These needs encompass the desire for recognition, respect, achievement, autonomy, and independence.

Self-actualization needs: At the highest levels of Maslow's need theory, individuals aspire to achieve their full potential and engage in self-development. Maslow posits that once a need is satisfied, it ceases to serve as a motivator for an individual's behavior, and they become driven by needs at the next higher level in the hierarchy.

Despite Maslow's valuable contributions and insights into motivational theories, subsequent research endeavors have struggled to provide robust support for need-based theories. Efforts to validate the hierarchical structure

proposed by Maslow's hierarchy have also encountered challenges in obtaining conclusive evidence. Nonetheless, the hierarchy model continues to be appealing to many.

“Herzberg two factor theory” (1959):

“Herzberg, Mausner and Snyderman(1959)” developed the “two-factor theory”, primarily focusing on fulfilling employees' needs and striving to enhance their satisfaction. They conducted numerous studies aimed at identifying the factors that bring satisfaction and dissatisfaction among white-collar workers. Their research revealed that the factors leading to job satisfaction, when present, are distinct from those causing dissatisfaction when absent. As a result, they viewed job satisfaction and dissatisfaction as separate entities. They coined the term “hygiene factors” to describe the environmental elements responsible for worker dissatisfaction.

The presence of these factors according to Herzberg et al., (1959) the presence of these hygiene factors, which encompass company policy, administration, technical supervision, salary, interpersonal relationships with supervisors, and work conditions, did not generate satisfaction and failed to boost the performance of white-collar workers. These hygiene factors were deemed essential but not sufficient for worker satisfaction. Furthermore, Herzberg and his colleagues identified motivating factors as the elements that stimulate increased effort from workers. They linked these factors to the nature of the job itself, emphasizing what individuals do in their work. These motivating factors were categorized as Achievement, Recognition, the nature of the work itself, Responsibility, and Advancement. Achievement was associated with the desire for excellence and the pursuit of personal growth and advancement.

“Theory X & Y (Douglas McGregor)”(1960, n.d.)

Effort can be elicited not only through external control and coercion; individuals are also capable of exercising self-direction and self-discipline to attain their goals.

The level of dedication to goals is influenced by the magnitude of rewards associated with their accomplishment.

Given suitable circumstances, humans not only acquire responsibility but also embrace it as part of their development.

“Theory of needs – Achievement theory (David C. McClelland -1961)”

McClelland and Associates proposed that some individuals possess a strong inner drive for personal success, which leads them to pursue personal achievement rather than seeking the rewards of success itself. These individuals aspire to continually outperform themselves, demonstrating a preference for challenging tasks and displaying characteristics typical of high achievers. This theory primarily centers on the concept of achievement, thus it is known as the achievement theory. However, it is based on a combination of achievement, power, and affiliation motives:

“Achievement: This pertains to the motivation to excel and surpass the established standards of success”.

“Power”: This reflects the “desire to make an impact, exert influence, and control the actions of others”.

“Affiliation”: It represents the yearning for forming warm and “close interpersonal relationships”.

“ERG Theory” (Alderfer, Clayton” P-1969, n.d.)

“Clayton Alderfer” (1969) conducted research that built upon Maslow's theory, offering practical insights.

“Alderfer restructured Maslow's hierarchy of needs into three categories: Existence, Relatedness, and Growth, and named it the ERG theory. In this categorization, he includes Maslow's delineation of needs as follows: Existence (covering physiological and security needs), Relatedness (encompassing social and esteem needs), and Growth (encompassing self-actualization)”.

Alderfer's model introduces a continuum of needs, departing from the hierarchical levels or the concept that one need must be satisfied before a higher-level need can serve as a motivator. Moreover, unlike Maslow and Herzberg, Alderfer does not posit that deprivation is the sole mechanism for triggering a need.

“Process theories”

“Process theories delve into the mechanics of motivation. Expectancy, a central concept in cognitive theory, plays a vital role in process theories of job satisfaction”; explaining how needs and goals are cognitively fulfilled. These theories have been proposed and tested, sparking considerable interest among researchers. Well-known models for process motivation include:

(i) *“Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964)”*

“Victor H. Vroom posits that individuals are driven to engage in work to attain a goal when they perceive that the goal is valuable, and they believe that their actions can contribute to achieving that goal”. Vroom's theory revolves around three key variables: Valence, Expectancy, and Instrumentality. Valence represents the intensity of an individual's preference or the value they place on a specific outcome, incentive, attitude, or expected

utility. Expectancy pertains to the likelihood that a given effort will result in a particular initial outcome, while Instrumentality relates to the extent to which an initial outcome will lead to a desired second-level outcome.

(ii) *“Equity theory (Adams, 1963)”*

This theory proposes that “employees assess the effort they invest in a job (input) in comparison to the rewards they receive (outcome), and then they contrast this ratio with the input-outcome ratio of their peers”. If they discover that this ratio matches that of their relevant colleagues, it is considered a state of equity (Adams & Jacobsen, 1964).

(iii) *Goal setting theory (Locke, 1968, n.d.)*

This model is a commonly acknowledged explanation of the job satisfaction process. Porter and Lawler stress that the “degree of effort (the intensity or strength of motivation) does not directly result in performance. Rather, it is affected by an employee's skills, characteristics, and their perception of their role”. Moreover, job satisfaction is not contingent on performance; rather, it is determined by the likelihood of receiving equitable rewards.

Edwin Locke's Goal-Setting Theory, introduced in the late 1960s, posits that intentions can be a significant source of motivation and satisfaction. Specific goals or intentions can lead to improved performance. For instance, challenging goals, when accepted, lead to higher performance compared to easily achievable goals, and receiving feedback enhances performance more than having no feedback.

(iv) *“Self-Determination Theory (Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan-1985, n.d.)”*

Self-Determination Theory (SDT), introduced by Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan in 1985, is a prominent framework in motivation psychology. It posits that individuals have innate psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, and their motivation is driven by fulfilling these needs. SDT has been widely applied in various fields, including education, workplace management, and healthcare, offering insights into how to foster intrinsic motivation and well-being. Researchers have explored the role of autonomy support, feedback, and social context in enhancing motivation and performance, making SDT a valuable tool in understanding human behavior and motivation.

“Job Characteristic theory (Hackman & Oldham, 1975-76)”

Job characteristics encompass the elements within an employee's role and tasks that influence how the individual views their specific position within the organization. Hackman and Oldham's (1980) initial concept of the job characteristics theory contended that the effects of job redesign were subject to multiple moderating factors. These moderators involve variances in the extent to which employees aspire to personal or psychological development. Enhanced role clarity contributes to higher job satisfaction since increased role clarity fosters a workforce that, in turn, heightens the probability of attaining desired outcomes.

“Reinforcement theories” (B.F Skinner, 1989)

Reinforcement theories operate on the premise that an individual's actions are shaped by their perception of the positive or negative outcomes associated with those actions. These outcomes can take the form of tangible rewards, like financial compensation, or intangible ones, such as verbal praise. In this context, reinforcement theory played a pivotal role in solidifying the concepts related to incentive and reward systems that are commonly utilized in modern organizations. It laid the foundation for the idea that rewards should be linked to an individual's level of productivity.

Understanding job satisfaction is essential for management to enhance the overall performance of the organization (Putman, 2002). Hoppock, as referenced in (Alromaihi, ..., & 2017), was among the early pioneers who introduced the concept of job satisfaction. He described job satisfaction as 'a blend of psychological, physiological, and environmental conditions that lead an individual to genuinely express contentment with their job. In the education sector, optimizing employee performance is a constant priority. Educational institutions aim to employ innovative strategies that motivate educators to excel, enhancing both student outcomes and overall institutional productivity (Akram, Javed, Niaz, & Mahmood, 2022). Challenges within organizations, such as time limitations, emphasize the significance of educator performance. Effective performance in the field of education showcases educators' commitment to their responsibilities and their contributions toward realizing the objectives and missions of the institution. Key indicators of educator performance include compensation practices, performance evaluations, and promotion procedures (Woulfin & Spitzer, 2023).

Educator performance holds significant importance, especially for classroom-based educators and can be influenced by various internal and external factors (Looney, Cumming, ..., & 2017). To enhance educator performance, educational institutions should investigate external factors affecting it. Strategies for improvement

may involve workload management through increased staffing, creating balanced work-week structures for a healthier work-life balance, and promoting educators regularly to boost job satisfaction. Proper educator placement, aligning skills and interests, contributes to peak job performance. Performance appraisals conducted by managers play a pivotal role in evaluating and shaping future policies based on educator performance. Continuous monitoring ensures that educators work effectively and efficiently to meet their objectives. Factors like organizational culture, engagement, and motivation significantly influence educator performance. Organizational culture, in particular, shapes behavior and problem-solving within educational institutions, fostering adaptability and unity among staff. Compensation, encompassing monetary payments and service rewards for educators' involvement, is also integral to the equation (Mehralian, Sheikhi, Zatzick, & Babapour, 2023).

In education, educator performance is characterized by the quality and quantity of work accomplished in fulfilling their teaching responsibilities. Ultimately, educator performance in the education sector is a multifaceted process reflecting the input, methods, output, and outcomes of educators' efforts. In this study, employee work performance is assessed across five key dimensions: Task Execution, Quality of Work, Problem Solving and Adaptability, Communication and Collaboration, and Time Management.

Task Execution: This dimension refers to an employee's ability to complete tasks and assignments on time and with attention to detail. It is a fundamental aspect of job performance and is often studied in the context of performance appraisal and goal-setting theories.

Quality of Work: The quality of work dimension focuses on the level of excellence and precision in an employee's outputs. Researchers like Edwin A. Locke have explored the impact of goal-setting on the quality of work.

Problem-Solving and Adaptability: This dimension relates to an employee's ability to identify and address work-related challenges and to adapt to changes in the work environment. It is relevant to research on employee resilience and coping strategies.

Communication and Collaboration: Communication and collaboration skills are crucial for effective teamwork and organizational success. Researchers often study these dimensions in the context of team dynamics and interpersonal relationships.

Time Management: Time management involves efficiently allocating time to tasks and responsibilities, meeting deadlines, and managing interruptions. This dimension is studied in the context of productivity and work efficiency.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

As indicated by the study's key findings, a conceptual model was developed. The diagram representing this conceptual model is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Conceptual/Structural model of the study.

This research aims to determine the relationship between Job satisfaction dimension and teachers work performance and to see which dimension are the predictors of teachers work performance. Most specifically, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- R1:** Is there any relationship between supervision and employee work performance?
- R2:** Is there any relationship between colleagues and employee work performance?
- R3:** Is there any relationship between working condition and employee work performance?
- R4:** Is there any relationship between salary and employee work performance?
- R5:** Is there any relationship between responsibility and employee work performance?
- R6:** Is there any relationship between work itself and employee work performance?
- R7:** Is there any relationship between advancement and employee work performance?
- R8:** Is there any relationship between security and employee work performance?
- R9:** Is there any relationship between recognition and employee work performance?
- R10:** Is there any relationship between overall job satisfaction and employee work performance?

The following null hypothesis was designed to be evaluated at 0.05 significant levels based on the above goals and study questions:

- H_a 1:** There is a significant relationship between supervision and employee work performance.
- H_a 2:** There is a significant relationship between colleagues and employee work performance.
- H_a 3:** There is a significant relationship between working condition and employee work performance.
- H_a 4:** There is a significant relationship between salary and employee work performance.
- H_a 5:** There is a significant relationship between responsibility and employee work performance.
- H_a 6:** There is a significant relationship between work itself and employee work performance.
- H_a 7:** There is a significant relationship between advancement and employee work performance.
- H_a 8:** There is a significant relationship between security and employee work performance.
- H_a 9:** There is a significant relationship between recognition and employee work performance.
- H_a 10:** There is a significant relationship between overall job satisfaction and employee work performance.

METHODOLOGY

The Survey Questionnaire

This exploratory study employed a quantitative research approach, comprising three main sections within the instrument: Section A, Section B, and Section C. Section A was dedicated to gathering background information from the respondents. In Section B, ten distinct constructs for measuring job satisfaction were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale. These constructs encompassed various aspects such as supervision, colleagues, working conditions, salary and incentives, responsibility, the nature of the work itself, advancement opportunities, job security, recognition, and overall job satisfaction. The questionnaire used in this section was adapted from Lester (1987) with the addition of an overall job satisfaction dimension.

Section C focused on evaluating work performance and included five constructs: task execution, quality of work, problem solving and adaptability, communication & collaboration and time management. These constructs were adapted from the work of different researcher. The reliability of the developed instruments was assessed, with the alpha value exceeding 0.70, indicating their reliability (Chin, 1988).

Participants and Procedures

This study treated job satisfaction as an independent variable and work performance as a dependent variable. The survey was conducted on the Islamia university teachers in Bahawalpur region, Pakistan. In this study, a random sample was selected, comprising 42 teaching staff members from the 8 departments of the educational faculty, 103 teachers from the 7 departments of the faculty of computing and 145 teachers were selected from department of management sciences. These individuals held various positions with different salary scales. According to the data from Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the total population for this study fell within the range of 290. However, the actual sample size used in the study was 165, as indicated by (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). This sample size met the minimum requirement for conducting a “structural equation model (SEM) analysis with the maximum likelihood (ML) estimation method”, which typically falls within the range of 150 to 400, as outlined by (Santoso, 2015).

In this research, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis was employed, utilizing a Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach. The study focuses on two latent variables: job satisfaction and work performance. Job

satisfaction has 10 manifest variables, namely, supervision, colleagues, working conditions, salary, responsibility, work itself, advancement, security, recognition and overall job satisfaction.

Work performance has five variables, namely, task execution, quality of work, problem solving and adaptability, communication and collaboration and "time management". The structural model was subsequently evaluated for both "internal and external validity" in order to ascertain the trustworthiness and credibility of the indicators employed for gauging latent variables. This outcome is depicted in Figure 2.

Out of the initial set of 10 dimensions, seven indicators were found to have values below 0.70, necessitating their removal. These dimensions included supervision, colleagues, working conditions, salary, security, recognition, and overall job satisfaction, with the exception of the dimension related to the nature of the work itself.

Among the 5 work performance indicators, two were removed from the analysis: communication & collaboration, and time management. The dimension of problem solving and adaptability retained a value of 0.448, indicating its significance in the analysis.

“Convergent Validity”

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for every variable exceeded 0.5, confirming the convergent validity of all “latent or construct variables”. You can find the AVE values for each variable in Table 1.

“Discriminant Validity”

“The square root of AVE” was greater than the correlation value of the latent variable with all other latent variables. The correlation value of each latent variable can be seen in Table 2.

For all latent variables, including job satisfaction and work performance, it was noted that the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) surpassed the correlation value with other latent variables. This observation confirms that the criteria for discriminant validity between these two variables in the study were satisfied.

“Variants of “Endogenous Variables”

The R-squared (R2) value serves as a measure to assess the degree of changes caused by "independent variables on dependent variables." If the R2 value reaches .75, the structural model falls into the strong category, while an R2 value of .50 designates it as moderate, and an R2 value of .25 classifies it as weak.

The outcomes of the R2 values are presented in Table 3. Specifically, the R2 value for the job satisfaction (JS) variable was 50%. This indicates that the job satisfaction variable accounted for 50% of the variance in the relationship between job satisfaction and work performance.

Figure 2. Results with all dimensions.

In this study, researcher investigated the simultaneous influence of employee job satisfaction on teachers' work performance. The study found that job satisfaction, in conjunction with work performance, explained 50% of the variance in the initial model. However, after removing dimensions with low values, the R-squared value decreased to 30%. The remaining 70% of the variance was attributed to unexamined factors.

Figure 3. Results with removing dimensions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

“Table 1”. AVE Value”.

“Description	JS	WP	“Evidence”
CR	0.756	0.677	“Reliable”
Cronbach’s α	0.734	0.673	Reliable
AVE	0.529	0.426	Reliable
Full collinearity VIF	1.955	1.370	“Reliable”

Note. “CR >0.67; CA >0.67; AVE > 0.5; VIF > 1.0.” AVE = average variance extracted”; JS = job satisfaction; WP = work performance; CR = composite reliability; AVE = average variance extracted; VIF = variance inflation factor”.

Table 2. Fornell-Lacker Criteria.

Variable	JS	WP
JS	0.727	
WP	0.549	0.653

Note. JS = job satisfaction; WP = work performance.

“Table 3”. Results of R square test”.

Variable	R ²	AdjustedR ²	criteria
WP	0.301	0.294	Moderate/Weaker

Note. JS = job satisfaction; WP = work performance.

“Table 4. Results of Path Coefficient Test”.

Variable	JS	WP
JS		0.549
WP		

Note. JS = job satisfaction; WP = work performance.

“Table 5. “Results of Bootstrapping Test”

Hypothesis	“Original sample”	SE	“T-statistics (O/SE)”	p	“Decision”
JS →WP	0.549	0.131	4.191	0.000	Accepted

Note. JS = job satisfaction; WP = work performance.

“The Significance of the Structural Model”

A test of significance was performed to evaluate the influence of the connection between dependent and independent variables, with the results detailed in Table 4. Upon scrutinizing the results of the path coefficient test from the initial sample column, several noteworthy discoveries emerge. Job satisfaction had a positive influence on teachers' work performance, with a coefficient of 0.30. This indicates that for each increment in job satisfaction, employee work performance improves by 30%.

Hypothesis Testing (Bootstrapping)

For hypothesis testing using bootstrapping, a significance level of 0.05 (5%) was employed. The outcomes presented in Table 5 furnished "statistical figures and p-values" as the foundation for either endorsing or refuting the suggested hypotheses. If the T-statistics surpass 1.90, the hypothesis is embraced; otherwise, it is discarded.

An alternative method for hypothesis acceptance is to consider the p-value, with a p-value less than 0.05 signifying acceptance of the hypothesis. The table demonstrates that Job satisfaction significantly influences teachers' work performance, with a “T-statistics value” of 4.191 and a “p-value of less than 0.05”, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis.

These findings from the analysis indicate that job satisfaction has a positive and statistically significant direct impact on the performance of government personnel. The positive influence of job satisfaction on employees is reflected in their ability to make a positive impression while carrying out their job responsibilities. As a result, this leads to considerable improvements in employee performance. Naturally, employees' success in executing their job responsibilities, resulting in satisfactory outcomes, positively contributes to their overall morale, ultimately fostering high levels of performance.

The findings of this study align with previous research conducted by Memon, Khahro, Memon, Memon, & Mustafa (2023), Wahid & Fadlallah (2015), Baluyos, Rivera, & Baluyos (2019), Rachman & Rachman (2021), Mahmood & Ismail (2018), M. & Durai (2017) and (Mahmood et al., 2020). These studies all indicate that when employees' expectations for job satisfaction are met, and they are able to perform their work according to their skills and expertise, it leads to positive outcomes in their work. As a result, employees achieve higher levels of performance, independence in their work, and timely completion of assigned tasks by the organization. Factors such as fair promotion opportunities, a reasonable compensation system that matches the nature of the work, and good working conditions contribute to enhanced employee performance. In essence, employee job satisfaction has a positive impact on their performance, a conclusion supported by other research findings (Nimalathasan, Brabete, Nimalathasan, & Brabete, 2010).

Furthermore, as suggested by Misra & Srivastava (2023), organizational changes can influence the workplace environment, either positively or negatively, which in turn affects the health, safety, and overall well-being of employees. This, in turn, indirectly contributes to employee satisfaction. Consequently, employee performance indirectly influences job satisfaction by improving the workplace, especially in terms of creating a "happy" atmosphere.

Figure 4. Excellent JS and WP Model.

Note. JS = job satisfaction; WP = work performance.

CONCLUSION

Teacher work performance was impacted both directly and indirectly by job satisfaction among employees. In particular, job satisfaction exerted a more significant influence on teacher work performance through factors like advancement, responsibility, and the nature of the work itself.

Job satisfaction significantly influenced teachers work performance on the dimensions of Problem-Solving and Adaptability, Quality of Work, Task Execution, Communication and Collaboration and Time Management, while the aspects of communication and collaboration, as well as time management, could not be determined due to the testing results being inconclusive and lacking reliability.

Advancement and Quality of Work: A positive relationship between "Advancement" and "Quality of Work" suggests that when employees or teachers perceive opportunities for career advancement and growth, it can positively influence the quality of their work. For example, when teachers believe that their career is advancing, they may be more motivated to deliver high-quality work.

Responsibility and Task Execution: Furthermore, This path coefficient represents the relationship between the "Responsibility" dimension of job satisfaction and the "Task Execution" dimension of work performance. Similar to the previous interpretation, a positive coefficient indicates that as job satisfaction with "Responsibility" increases, task execution tends to improve. Teachers who feel a greater sense of responsibility in their roles tend to execute tasks more effectively.

Work Itself and Problem Solving: In addition, the path coefficient indicates the relationship between the "Work Itself" dimension of job satisfaction and the "Problem Solving" dimension of work performance. A strong sense of "Responsibility" can lead to more effective "Task Execution." When individuals feel a strong sense of duty and responsibility in their roles, they are more likely to carry out their tasks thoroughly and efficiently. The relationship between "Work Itself" and "Problem Solving" might indicate that when individuals find their job tasks and responsibilities engaging and satisfying, they may be more creative and effective problem solvers. Job satisfaction with the nature of the work can lead to improved problem-solving abilities.

In this study, researcher investigated the simultaneous influence of employee job satisfaction on teachers' work performance. The study found that job satisfaction, in conjunction with work performance, explained 50% of the variance in the initial model. However, after removing dimensions with low values, the R-squared value decreased to 30%. The remaining 70% of the variance was attributed to unexamined factors. We found that job satisfaction plays a significant role in shaping teachers' work performance. Specifically, job satisfaction accounts for 30% of the variance in teachers' work performance. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the

remaining 70% of the variance in work performance is influenced by other variables, including but not limited to managerial performance, school climate, total quality management, employee self-efficacy, and other factors that have not been explored in this study.

Limitations and Future Research:

Variables Not Studied: As mentioned, our study primarily focused on the relationship between job satisfaction and work performance. Numerous other variables, such as the role of “managerial performance”, “school climate”, total quality management, employee self-efficacy, and more, may influence teachers' work performance. Future research should delve into these unexplored factors to gain a comprehensive understanding of what drives work performance among teachers.

Scope and Generalizability: Our study was limited to the university level in Pakistan. To enhance the generalizability of the findings, further research can be conducted among secondary school teachers and across different countries. This broader scope will help us gain insights into the variations in the impact of job satisfaction on work performance within various educational settings and cultural contexts.

Mediating and Moderating Factors: In addition to exploring new variables, future research should also consider potential mediating and moderating factors that could further elucidate the complex interrelationships between job satisfaction and work performance dimensions. For example, examining the role of motivation, leadership styles, or organizational culture as mediators or moderators could provide a deeper understanding of these dynamics.

By addressing these limitations and pursuing future research in these directions, we can better comprehend the multifaceted factors influencing teachers' work performance and, in turn, contribute to the development of more effective strategies to enhance job satisfaction and work performance in educational settings.

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